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**METHODS OF FORMING SIMPLE GEOMETRIC CONCEPTS IN CHILDREN
OF PRESCHOOL AGE**

**МЕТОДИКА ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ПРОСТЫХ ГЕОМЕТРИЧЕСКИХ ПОНЯТИЙ
У ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА**

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Abstract. The article, to consider that the formation of children's ideas about geometric shapes is evident in their ability to form perception. This ability allows the child to learn to distinguish and represent various geometric shapes. To develop in children the skills to identify geometric shapes in various objects of the world around us or find their similarity with geometric shapes. It helps in complete the world deliberately to examine the surrounding objects.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается что формирования детских представлений о геометрических фигурах проявляется их способности к восприятие форм. Эта способность позволяет ребенку научиться различать и представлять различные геометрические фигуры. Развивание у детей навыки определения геометрических фигур в различные предметах окружающего нас мира или находить их сходство с геометрическими фигурами. Это помогает в полной мере целенаправленно изучать окружающие нас предметы.

Keywords: geometric, shapes, thinking, worldview, preschool, education.

Ключевые слова: геометрические, фигуры, мышление, мировоззрение, дошкольная, образования.

Periodic of preschool education is the basis of the formation of knowledge, thinking and Outlook of personality, the formation of underpinnings of the physiology and psychology of the child.

For this reason, along with the issue of reproductive health of the child and development of the preschool education system, in our opinion, we must the work on formation of children the simplest concepts of geometric shapes, particularly paying attention to formation at them the basics of thinking and cognition in the world.

For the realization of this task, which is a harmonious addition to the education of children 3–4 years of age, you must use the didactic material in the form of multicolored, different sized

geometric shapes, such as square, round, triangle, which contribute to the formation of children simple ideas about geometric objects.

Before the system of exercises educator using geometric shapes or mosaic organizes games. It is a very important during this period of child development to provide basic concepts of geometric shapes and their differences. The main objectives of the exercise is to develop skills to distinguish a circle from a square, and their proper name by their comparison.

The first lesson in the study of figures and the methods of their presentation requires the prior introduction of geometric shapes of children by way of observation or demonstration. The teacher shows the figure calls him and asks to take the same model in his hands. In addition, the caregiver makes these figures different actions: circle performs a circular motion, checks for possible circular steps with squares. The same actions committed with figures of various colors, sizes and configurations.

In conclusion, to consolidate this material are held several exercises with questions: “What am I holding in his right hand and his left hand?”; “Little bear let the circle and the Bunny give me the square.” The following exercises are performed for securing the correct determination of the names and shapes geometric shapes:

A) the exercise help in collecting specimens: “Exactly the same (fetch, show, take, put)”;

B) exercises aimed at the selection of words (get, show, take, put, get etc);

C) exercises didactic and effective: “What is this?” “Fabulous bag”, “What lost?”, “Find your house”, and others of like nature.

Children up to five years in the first place it is necessary to distinguish and correctly identify the circle and the square, and then give the concept of a triangle. For a more sustainable consolidation of knowledge are different games with shapes of different sizes and colors for various groups. Change size and color of figures, but the main features of the shapes remain unchanged. It helps to develop children in General sustainable concept of the differences of figures.

To learn about the extent of the formation of children’s ideas about geometric shapes they show a different, previously studied forms. Of shows the children are taken previously studied shapes, both small and a large size. Comparing the size of various geometric shape (based on visual observation and comparison), children identify identical shapes, but different in the size of the structure. In the next activity children divided into three pieces and arrange them by size, the degree of decrease or increase.

Then children handed out individual envelopes with the shapes and ask to sort them by similarity and talk about them.

Thus, a continuously updated handout helps children separate the important characteristics of the investigated objects. Creating conditions for conducting a variety of exercises. The same exercise can be done with a new unknown geometric shapes.

Acquaintance of children with new geometric shapes is done by comparison with previously studied:

–regular quadrilateral with a square,

ball with the circle, and then with a cube

–the cube of a square, and then with the ball

–cylinder with the correct quadrilateral and a circle, then a sphere and a cube.

Study and a comparison of the figures is carried out in strict sequence:

1) the location of the pieces vertically or in a row; this gives the opportunity to determine distinctive feature: the similarities and differences of the objects under study;

2) study (study) figures. At this stage, the introduction of the figures is the method of their movements and understand specific elements and configurations. Efficiency study of the figures depends on the teacher explaining that impacts to some extent on the development in children of observation (definition of angles, their number, color, similarity of forms), which is an important element of learning the studied material.

3) to organize different movements with geometric shapes (swap, rolling circles, etc.). In the process of working with models, children determine their sustainability and give a physical description of the figures. For example, children try to place them in different positions the ball and the cylinder. They begin to understand that the cylinder can ride, put vertically stacked, and the ball can only be moved by crook.

4) organization of dividing the figures into groups based on the size of the small and large (“select external structure”, “select color”, “tidy”)

5) to develop and consolidate children’s skills of selection of shapes and their proper names, it is necessary to conduct didactic games (“what has changed”, “find a pair”, “secret pouch”, etc.).

On this basis, they learn about geometric shapes, identify and describe the external features of the studied structures. Also one of the main problems considered is the formation in children of a system of knowledge about geometric figures. This system can become the basis for a final generalization in the study of geometric figures and their characteristics.

In order to have children, we have strong confidence and belief in the study of the shapes can be described, the teacher shows these items in a magnifying scale.

It is necessary to develop in children the skills to identify geometric shapes in various objects of the world around us or find their similarity with geometric shapes. It helps in complete the world purposefully to explore the surrounding objects and display them in paintings, applique, create, sculpt from clay.

In conclusion, it is necessary to say that in the process of educational process children can distinguish the details of geometrical shapes.

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